

Reproducibility and reliability of renal image segmentation and radiomics: the AI4PKD project

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Abstract

Project “AI-based methods to improve stratification of patients affected by Polycystic Kidney Disease using multi-parametric MRI” (AI4PKD), funded within the PRIN 2022 program, aims at discovering MRI-based biomarkers to identify ADPKD stage, based on robust and reliable AI-based methods for the automatic analysis of Magnetic Resonance Images (MRI) from patients with Autosomal Dominant Polycystic Kidney Disease (ADPKD). This work presents the first two activities of the project, focused on developing automatic segmentation tools and radiomic analysis pipelines that may guarantee reproducibility and reliability of the analyses, which are essential for trustable and reliable application in the clinical field. On the one hand, we quantified the impact of segmentation and scan-rescan variability on radiomics reproducibility using T2-weighted kidney MRI scans. On the other hand, we assessed the reliability of radiomic features extracted from anatomical and diffusion MRI images of ADPKD patients. These analyses allowed us to identify the best setting to ensure robustness and reliability of the analyses for future extraction of the biomarkers.

Keywords

Radiomics, Renal MRI, Uncertainty quantification, Reproducibility

1 Introduction

Autosomal Dominant Polycystic Kidney Disease (ADPKD) is the most prevalent hereditary kidney disease, characterized by formation and growing of multiple fluid-filled cysts in the kidneys and often the liver, which lead to chronic kidney injury [1]. Total kidney volume and cyst volume currently represent the most relevant biomarkers to monitor disease progression, to assess response to therapy, and for prognosis. Besides, non-cystic renal parenchyma volume may provide additional relevant information about the presence of peritubular interstitial fibrosis, which was associated with renal function and its decline over time [1]. These indices can be effectively measured through non-contrast enhanced Magnetic Resonance Images (MRI). In particular, multi-parametric MRI (mp-MRI), which combines morphological and diffusion MRI, can quantify kidney and liver cysts, as well as non-invasively characterize the non-cystic component through the extraction of radiomic features. For this purpose, a fully automatic segmentation method to detect kidneys, liver and cysts in ADPKD patients able to exploit the multi-parametric information provided by anatomical and diffusion MRI would be desirable, but not fully available yet in the literature.

In this direction, project “AI-based methods to improve stratification of patients affected by Polycystic Kidney Disease using multi-parametric MRI” (AI4PKD), funded within the PRIN 2022 program, aims to discover novel MRI-based biomarkers that identify ADPKD stage, based on robust and reliable AI-based methods for the automatic analysis of abdominal mp-MRI images of ADPKD patients. In fact, despite AI methods are increasingly adopted in the context of medical imaging, such as deep learning and radiomics, only preliminary results have been presented for ADPKD patients.

In the first part of the project, the activities focused on the development of tools that may guarantee reproducibility and reliability of the outcomes. On the one hand, we quantified the impact of segmentation and scan-rescan variability on radiomics reproducibility using T2-weighted MRI scans of kidneys (Section 2). In fact, segmentation and scan-rescan variability are known to affect radiomics robustness, with the latter having a predominant impact on radiomics robustness [2]. On the other hand, we assessed the reliability of radiomic features extracted from anatomical and diffusion MRI images of ADPKD patients (Section 3). In fact, despite radiomics has been recently proposed for classification and prediction of ADPKD stage and progression, it still suffers from robustness and stability issues. This paper summarizes the main findings of these two activities, which allowed us to identify the best setting, to ensure robustness and reliability of the analyses for the future extraction of biomarkers.

2 Impact of segmentation and scan-rescan variability on radiomics reproducibility

This activity analysed to what extent the quantification of segmentation uncertainty through Convolutional Neural Networks can address the scan-rescan

Figure 1: MRI slice with manual contour of the kidneys in green: CKD patient (a) and HC subject (b).

and segmentation variability that impact radiomics reliability. Specifically, we examined whether extracting features solely from confidently segmented regions may enhance radiomic robustness compared to extracting features from the segmented regions without accounting for segmentation uncertainty.

2.1 Materials and methods

The dataset consisted of T2-weighted coronal kidney MRI scans from 60 subjects from a public repository [3], including 30 patients with Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) and 30 Healthy Control (HC) individuals. This dataset also contained manually segmented kidney masks, which were considered the Ground Truth (GT). Ten subjects (5 HCs and 5 CKDs) underwent five independent scans within a single session; their images (650 2D slices) were used as test data and for the radiomic analysis. The data (649 2D slices) from the remaining 50 subjects (25 CKD, 25 HC), each scanned once, were used for training the models (80% training, 20% validation), along with their GT. An example is reported in Figure 1.

Kidney segmentation was performed using a 2D U-Net model [4]. Training parameters were: Dice score loss function; 100 epochs; batch size of 16; Adam optimizer with learning rate equal to 10^{-4} . Data augmentation with random shifts, zooms, rotations and shears was included. Two alternative approaches were then considered to estimate segmentation uncertainty. First, a Bayesian U-Net was adopted, which employs Monte Carlo Dropout (MCD) [5]. Indeed, dropout layers were introduced in the deterministic U-Net architecture and kept active during both training and inference, with dropout rate equal to 0.25. During inference, 50 MCD samples were generated through $T = 50$ forward passes across the network, producing stochastic predictions. Second, the deterministic U-Net was used at test time to make predictions over $T = 50$ different augmented versions of the input image [6]; this is denoted by Test Time Augmentation (TTA) in the following.

The Mean Prediction segmentation mask (MP) was computed as the pixel-wise mean, and then binarized. In addition, to draw masks that reflect different

Levels of Confidence in segmentation (CL masks), thresholds th for agreement among the 50 binarized predictions were established, ranging from 0.1 to 1 with a 0.1 step size. As th increases, more internal regions of the kidney are selected.

Radiomic features were extracted using package `Pyradiomics` in Python from GT, MP and CL masks. Reproducibility to segmentation variability was assessed using the Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC) [7] type 3 between manually and automatically delineated kidney regions (ICC_S); reproducibility to scan-rescan variability was assessed using the ICC type 2 among the five scan repetitions per subject on the kidney mask (ICC_A). Coefficients were first computed without including uncertainty information, considering the MP mask to compute ICC_S and the GT mask to compute ICC_A . Then, CL masks at different thresholds were used for both ICC computation to evaluate the impact of including uncertainty confidence information. Radiomic features were categorized into 4 classes: class 1 with $ICC_S \geq 0.8$ and $ICC_A \geq 0.8$; class 2 with $ICC_S \geq 0.8$ and $ICC_A < 0.8$; class 3 as the opposite of class 2; class 4 with $ICC_S < 0.8$ and $ICC_A < 0.8$. Analyses were performed considering HC and CKD subjects separately.

2.2 Results

MCD and TTA methods showed comparable segmentation accuracy: the Dice for MCD was 0.93 and 0.91 on HC and CKD subjects, respectively, while the Dice for TTA was 0.93 and 0.90 on HC and CKD subjects, respectively.

The number of robust features in each class, without uncertainty information and at different th are reported in Figure 2 for the two methods and for CKD and HC subjects separately. In all cases, the number of features in class 4 decreased as th increases, while the number of features in class 3 increased up to a certain optimal threshold th_{opt} . For HC subjects, the number of features in class 1 increased too. Finally, TTA predictions showed greater variability.

3 Reliability of radiomic features

In this activity, we proposed a new evaluation of radiomic reliability that relies on reproducible and informative features, considering three segmentation methods (manual and automatic) as a key source of variability. We proposed a novel framework to identify reliable radiomic features for the characterization of non-cystic tissue in ADPKD patients using mp-MRI, which integrates anatomical images (T1-weighted MRI and T2-weighted MRI) with IntraVoxel In-coherent Motion (IVIM) maps from Diffusion Weighted Imaging (DWI), which provides information regarding microstructure and perfusion tissue properties [8].

3.1 Materials and methods

The dataset for this activity included 14 ADPKD patients from a prospective longitudinal clinical study (EuroCYST Initiative), of which data from the Is-

Figure 2: Number of features in each class, without uncertainty information and at different th , for the two methods and for CKD and HC subjects separately. The circled th corresponds to the th_{opt} .

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Images were acquired with no contrast media injection following the protocol of the Consortium for Radiologic Imaging Studies of Polycystic Kidney Disease (CRISP) [9]. An example is reported in Figure 3a.

Pre-processing of T1-weighted and T2-weighted images included bias fields correction [10] and intensity normalization [11]. Affine registration was computed between anatomical and DWI images and between b-values using Elastix [12]. IVIM parametric maps (D , f and D^*) were derived from DWI images through a supervised fully connected deep neural network (DNN) [13]. An example is reported in Figure 3b.

Non-cystic tissue was segmented using a manually obtained GT, and a Deep Learning Network for identifying cysts on T2-weighted images [14] in which the non-cystic region was obtained by subtracting the cystic tissue from the total kidney volume (DL^{start}). In addition, a post-processed version (DL^{adj}) was created by removing vessels, fat, and haemorrhagic cysts with mp-MRI. The agreement between any automatic segmentation and the manual GT was quantified using the Dice score.

Figure 3: Example of images from a patient: T1-weighted MRI, T2-weighted MRI and image b0 of the DWI acquisitions, with the GT contour in green (a). IVIM parametric maps for the same case (b).

A total of 92 radiomic features were extracted using package `Pyradiomics` on each image and segmentation method, considering the two kidneys separately. Radiomic feature reliability was assessed across segmentations with the ICC type 3 [7]. An $ICC \geq 0.8$ between GT and DL^{adj} was considered indicative of a reproducible radiomic feature, as extracted from regions with similar information content. An $ICC < 0.5$ between GT and DL^{start} was considered informative for characterizing non-cystic tissue, as extracted from regions with distinct information content. Finally, the percentage of reliable (i.e., reproducible and informative) features was determined for each alternative segmentation.

3.2 Results

Mean ICC scores over all features are reported in Table 1. They show higher reliability for the DL^{adj} segmentation, especially for IVIM maps. Segmentation DL^{adj} exhibited lower reproducibility for T1-weighted and T2-weighted images, while for these images DL^{start} showed higher ICC values. The percentage of reliable features for each image type, grouped by radiomic feature classes, is reported in Figure 4. The most reliable are First Order (FO) and Gray-Level Co-Occurrence Matrix (GLCM) features for D and f parametric maps, as well as Neighbouring Gray Tone Difference Matrix (NGTDM) features for D parametric map and Gray-Level Size Zone Matrix (GLSZM) for f map. Moreover, T1-weighted and T2-weighted images showed remarkably lower reliabilities than the other images.

		GT	DL^{start}	DL^{adj}
D	GT	1.00	0.26	0.81
	DL^{start}	0.26	1.00	0.30
	DL^{adj}	0.81	0.30	1.00
f	GT	1.00	0.28	0.86
	DL^{start}	0.28	1.00	0.28
	DL^{adj}	0.86	0.28	1.00
D^*	GT	1.00	0.41	0.89
	DL^{start}	0.41	1.00	0.43
	DL^{adj}	0.89	0.43	1.00
T1-w	GT	1.00	0.70	0.51
	DL^{start}	0.70	1.00	0.40
	DL^{adj}	0.51	0.40	1.00
T2-w	GT	1.00	0.61	0.49
	DL^{start}	0.61	1.00	0.69
	DL^{adj}	0.49	0.69	1.00

Table 1: ICC values averaged across all the radiomics features for D , f , D^* , T1-weighted and T2-weighted images, and for the different segmentations.

4 Conclusion

The first activity (Section 2) addressed the challenge of reproducibility in radiomic features due to variability in image segmentation and scan-rescan acquisitions, by proposing an automatic approach based on segmentation confidence evaluation. Results showed that, while scan-rescan variability consistently affects outcomes, segmentation variability is more pronounced in CKD patients due to lower accuracy. Extracting features from the most confident regions reduces scan-rescan variability for both HC and CKD subjects, and decreases segmentation variability only for HC individuals, remarking the importance of accurate segmentation. We can therefore conclude that integrating segmentation uncertainty evaluation into the radiomics workflow could enhance radiomic analysis robustness. The second activity (Section 3) pioneered radiomic reliability assessment in non-cystic tissue of ADPKD patients. Radiomics extracted from IVIM parametric maps offered improved ability to assess micro-structural tissue organization and composition compared to standard T1-weighted and T2-weighted scans. Radiomic features showed good reliability for D and f maps, moderate reliability for D^* maps, and unreliability for T1-weighted and T2-weighted scans, thereby suggesting to use of DWI for future analyses on ADPKD patients.

Our results show the possibility of guaranteeing reproducibility and reliability of automatic segmentation tools and radiomic analysis pipelines, which can support the potential diffusion of imaging for ADPKD characterization in the

Figure 4: Percentage of reliable features for each image type, grouped by radiomic feature classes: First Order (FO); Gray-Level Co-Occurrence Matrix (GLCM); Gray-Level Dependence Matrix (GLDM); Gray-Level Run Length Matrix (GLRLM); Gray-Level Size Zone Matrix (GLSZM); Neighbouring Gray Tone Difference Matrix (NGTDM).

clinical field. However, for both activities, the small sample size could limit the generalizability of the results. Therefore, more images will be considered in the future to increase the sample size and generalize the results.

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